

Decision making under deep uncertainty in long-term energy planning: A review and hybrid deliberation-with-analysis workflow

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Keywords

Decision making under deep uncertainty; robust decision making; deep uncertainty; adaptive pathways; stakeholder engagement; uncertainty analysis; energy system modelling; energy planning

Abstract

Long-term energy planning is a decision-making challenge under deep uncertainty. This systematic review assesses how Decision Making under Deep Uncertainty (DMDU) approaches are applied in energy planning and proposes a hybrid deliberation-with-analysis workflow to support adaptive, stakeholder-informed decisions. The review covers electricity, buildings, heating, transport, and cross-sector systems. A structured search identified 474 records; 158 full texts were screened, yielding 39 studies (2016–2026). Applications are concentrated in high-income, data-rich, and institutionally mature contexts, with limited use in lower- and middle-income countries. Among DMDU approaches, Exploratory Modelling and Analysis (EMA; 36% of studies) and Robust Decision Making (RDM; 31% of studies) are the most commonly used. Uncertainty treatment is predominantly parametric rather than structural. Although many studies assess robustness and identify vulnerabilities, these insights are rarely translated into adaptive, implementable decisions co-developed with stakeholders. Stakeholder engagement is often limited or absent, even in decision-oriented analyses. In response, this paper proposes a hybrid workflow integrating participatory problem framing, exploratory modelling, vulnerability analysis, and robustness assessment, culminating in the co-development of adaptive strategies. The framework emphasises iterative, cyclical engagement between analysis and deliberation to translate uncertainty insights into practical decision support. It provides a structured pathway for embedding stakeholder input and adaptive design into long-term energy planning under deep uncertainty.

1. Introduction

Long-term energy planning is fundamentally a decision-making problem under deep uncertainty [1], [2]. Policymakers must commit to infrastructure investments, technology pathways, and decarbonisation strategies whose consequences unfold over decades, while future socio-economic conditions, technological change, political commitment, and climate impacts remain contested.

In such settings, uncertainty is not only parametric but also structural, where analysts and stakeholders may disagree about system boundaries, model structures, and causal relationships. Building on the original uncertainty typologies [3], these describe deep uncertainty as conditions where there is uncertainty about external drivers, system relationships, and valuation of outcomes [4]. Under such conditions, probabilities are not reliably known and even the appropriate representation of future context, system behaviour, and stakeholder values may be contested.

In the presence of deep uncertainty, conventional predict-then-optimize approaches risk producing strategies that are brittle when the future diverges from the assumed baseline. The challenge is particularly acute for capital-intensive, long-lived, and path-dependent infrastructure systems, such as energy, water, and transport. Decision Making under Deep Uncertainty (DMDU) supports decisions in precisely these contexts. Rather than optimising for a single forecast, DMDU approaches embrace futures pluralism and use exploratory modelling—computational experiments designed to reason about systems with significant uncertainty—to evaluate candidate policies across large ensembles of plausible future conditions. This shift reframes uncertainty analysis from reducing uncertainty to learning how strategies perform across uncertainty, including identifying which combinations of assumptions drive failure and what trade-offs arise among objectives [5].

Across DMDU approaches, a typical workflow [4] begins with problem framing, followed by exploratory uncertainty analysis that parameterises salient uncertainties and disagreements about external drivers and, where feasible, alternative system representations. Analysts then diagnose vulnerabilities by identifying the uncertainty combinations under which strategies fail to meet thresholds, evaluate robustness across the ensemble of futures, and use these insights to redesign strategies or specify adaptive pathways with monitoring and contingent actions. Because the process is inherently iterative, the analysis is revisited as new options, problem framings, or stakeholder priorities emerge.

Several DMDU approaches are particularly influential. Robust Decision Making (RDM), advanced by Robert J. Lempert and colleagues at the RAND Corporation, runs large databases of model experiments and applies scenario-discovery analytics to iteratively improve strategies that perform acceptably across many futures [1]. Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways (DAPP) [6] represents plans as sequences of actions over time, using adaptation tipping points and explicit “signals” to indicate when to switch actions or reassess the plan. Exploratory Modelling and Analysis (EMA) [5], rooted in the exploratory modelling tradition, provides methodologies and tools for systematically exploring uncertainty spaces and policy levers via computational experiments. Finally, Info-Gap Decision Theory (IGDT) formalises robustness as the largest uncertainty “horizon” around a best estimate over which performance requirements are satisfied [7].

DMDU is decision-centred and commonly embedded within participatory processes. Many applications adopt “deliberation with analysis,” linking stakeholder deliberation with quantitative exploration so that uncertainties, objectives, and robustness trade-offs are co-produced and revisited as insights accumulate [8].

Achieving ambitious decarbonisation targets is a decision problem under deep uncertainty, because decisions in energy subsectors, such as electricity, transport, buildings, and industry are tightly coupled. In this review, energy planning is interpreted broadly to include electricity system decarbonisation, renewable energy investment, grid and storage expansion, carbon capture and storage, and related

cross-sectoral domains that directly influence emissions trajectories. Uncertainties in one domain frequently propagate across others, reinforcing the need for exploratory and robust decision frameworks.

A cross-sectoral review assessed the performance of DMDU methods in diverse policy contexts characterised by deep uncertainty, underscoring their broad applicability [9]. A growing body of literature recognises that energy transitions must move beyond predict-then-optimize paradigms toward robustness and adaptive planning [9], [10], [11], [12]. These studies emphasise that deep uncertainty in low-carbon transitions is multi-dimensional—spanning technological, socio-political, economic, and climate factors—and note that practical applications of DMDU approaches remain uneven and limited in scope [10], [11]. In parallel, robust and adaptive risk analysis methods have been synthesised conceptually [13], and specific approaches such as IGDT have been reviewed within energy-system contexts [14]. Existing reviews have provided methodological insights and broad sectoral perspectives, as well as important discussions of uncertainty within optimisation-based energy modelling frameworks [15].

Building on these contributions, this systematic review maps how DMDU approaches are operationalised in long-term energy planning models across geographies, sectors, decision levels, and uncertainty dimensions. It examines how deep uncertainty is translated into model-representable parameters, which uncertainty dimensions are parameterised, how vulnerability and robustness are assessed, and at what decision levels (e.g., project, portfolio, national strategy) these methods are deployed—thereby adding an application-focused perspective to existing conceptual and methodological syntheses.

2. Methods

This systematic review examines how uncertainty is operationalised in applied energy modelling studies for long-term planning and how this contributes to decision support. A systematic bibliographic search was conducted to identify studies applying DMDU approaches in long-term energy and climate mitigation planning. The search was performed across IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, ProQuest, SSRN, OSF, and OpenAlex databases.

The search strategy combined three concept blocks:

- (1) energy and climate mitigation planning contexts;
- (2) DMDU methodologies (e.g., Robust Decision Making, Info-Gap Decision Theory, Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways, scenario discovery, robust optimisation); and
- (3) deep or non-probabilistic uncertainty terminology.

Boolean operators and proximity functions were used to ensure conceptual precision, while water-sector operations and short-term dispatch studies were excluded. The search returned 474 records prior to screening. The complete Boolean search string is provided in Appendix A. These records were screened based on title and abstract, applying the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 1). Following this screening stage, 158 studies were retained for full-text assessment using the Rayyan systematic review platform.

Table 1. Selection criteria for the systematic review.

Selection criteria		
Inclusion	(i) (ii)	DMDU case study applied to the energy sector for long-term planning; published after 2016.
Exclusion	(i) (ii) (iii) (iv)	Case study was intended as illustrative, without real-world implementation; lacked an explicit DMDU framing or approach; were published as book chapters; were unavailable in full-text form.

From an initial pool of 158 articles, full-text screening was conducted to systematically extract characteristics of the study such as DMDU approaches, case study type, geographical application, sectoral focus, time horizon, spatial scale of reported results, decision level, and target users of insights, along with brief methodological remarks.

Subsequently, studies were excluded if they: (i) did not specify a geographical application (i.e., purely illustrative or methodological demonstrations without real-world implementation); (ii) were not applied to the energy sector; (iii) relied exclusively on deterministic or traditional robust optimisation without an explicit DMDU framing [16]; (iv) did not explicitly reference or operationalise a DMDU approach; (v) were book chapters; or (vi) were unavailable in full-text form.

The review period (2016–2026) was selected to capture the post-Paris Agreement. Building on foundational methodological contributions (Walker et al., 2013; Kwakkel et al., 2016; Marchau et al., 2019), the post-2015 literature increasingly reflects a shift toward applied, model-based operationalisation of DMDU approaches. Following screening, 39 papers were retained. A second-stage systematic data extraction was then undertaken, focusing on the uncertainty dimensions operationalised in each study and the associated decision outcomes, including the techniques employed for vulnerability analysis and robustness assessment, as well as the extent and nature of stakeholder involvement.

3. Results

Building on prior conceptual and methodological reviews [10], [11], [13], [14], [15], this section examines how DMDU approaches are operationalised in applied long-term energy planning studies. Specifically, it analyses which uncertainty dimensions are parameterised, how robustness and vulnerability are assessed, and at which decision levels these methods are implemented.

3.1 Characteristics of the reviewed studies

Figure 1 presents the number of DMDU papers published by method and case study geography. Across the reviewed studies ($n = 39$), EMA-based approaches are most prevalent [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], including variants such as those closely based on EMA [20], ESDMA (Exploratory System Dynamics Modeling and Analysis) [26], and EMA + EMODPS (Evolutionary Multi-Objective Direct Policy Search) [27]. EMA applications span strategy, system, national, and investment levels, demonstrating methodological flexibility across decision scales. RDM-based approaches form the second-largest group [30], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40] including RDM-inspired studies [30], [34], [36] and conceptual applications [40]. RDM is predominantly applied at the strategy and system levels, reflecting its suitability for long-term

infrastructure and policy analysis. A novel method named ROSS (based on RDM) is used in one study [41]. DAPP appears exclusively in six studies [42], [43], [44], [45], [46], [47], primarily at the strategy and policy levels, consistent with its emphasis on adaptive planning and sequencing of actions. Hybrid approaches remain limited, including EMA + DAPP [48] and DAP + RDM [49], while DAP alone appears in two studies [50], [51]. IGDT is used in four studies [52], [53], [54], [55], largely at the system and investment levels, suggesting more technically focused applications.

Figure 1. Trends in DMDU approaches

Applications increase markedly after 2020, with the majority of EMA studies published between 2020–2024. RDM applications also show recent growth. Earlier studies (2016–2018) are more commonly IGDT or narrative DAPP. The literature shows a transition from single-method applications toward exploratory and hybrid frameworks in the post-2020 period.

As shown in Figure 2, applications are concentrated in high-income countries, including the UK [31], [40], [42], [46], United States [27], [29], [37], [39], [52], Netherlands [19], [22], [43], [44], Sweden [28], [49], [51], France [36], [47], Germany [23], [55], Switzerland [18], [30], Australia [21], [50], and Japan [34]. LMIC representation is comparatively limited, including Brazil [54], Iran [53], India [17], Costa Rica [32], [33], Turkey [35], Dominican Republic [38], Indonesia [24], [25], [26], and China [38]. Overall, the evidence suggests that DMDU applications remain dominated in high-income countries, with increasing methodological diversification post-2020 and a strong concentration in strategy- and system-level energy planning contexts.

Figure 2. Geographical locations of the reviewed studies.

3.2 Uncertainties considered

The identification and operationalisation of uncertainty in DMDU can be synthesised into three core steps. First, the decision context is defined, including planning horizon, system boundaries, decision levers, and performance metrics (step 1: decision framing). Second, the uncertainty space is characterised by distinguishing among epistemic, aleatory, parametric, structural, and scenario uncertainties [56], [57], [58], clarifying which uncertainties may be reduced and which must be robustly managed (step 2: uncertainty typology). Third, key uncertainty parameters are translated into model-representable dimensions—such as techno-economic, socio-economic, political, technological, and climate variables—aligned with the decision problem and policy levers (step 3: operationalisation).

While Steps 1 and 2 establish the conceptual foundations of uncertainty analysis, Step 3 reflects what modelling studies implement in practice. In real-world DMDU applications—particularly in energy system modelling—the theoretical classification of uncertainty is often implicit, whereas its operationalisation is explicit and measurable through parameterisation and stress-testing. Accordingly, this review focuses specifically on how uncertainty is operationalised in applied modelling studies. It therefore concentrates on uncertainties that are formally parameterised, explored, and stress-tested within model-based applications, rather than those discussed solely at a conceptual level.

Table 2 summarises the uncertainties considered in the reviewed studies. Techno-economic uncertainties dominate the reviewed studies, particularly capital investment costs, fuel prices, and storage costs across electricity and energy system models. Financial parameters such as the discount rate are treated as uncertain in only a limited number of cases [35], [49], while transmission costs and grid losses remain comparatively underrepresented. Climate uncertainty appears less frequently and is concentrated mainly in hydropower modelling and electricity system studies [27], [32], [35], [37].

Socio-economic uncertainty is largely framed around macroeconomic growth and demand parameters—such as GDP growth, energy intensity, and electricity demand growth—especially in power-sector models [19], [33], [34], [38], [53], [54]. Behavioural uncertainty is incorporated in a small subset of operational and demand-side models [18], [20], [30], and several studies treat socio-economic and political uncertainties narratively rather than parametrically [45], [50].

Political and governance uncertainties are rarely quantified; only a few studies explicitly model institutional delays or long-term policy commitment [26], [46], [49]. Technological uncertainty is primarily focused on efficiency, performance, and learning effects, with storage and battery-related parameters frequently represented [20], [28], [38], while carbon capture performance appears in only two studies [46], [49].

Table 2. Uncertainties operationalised in the reviewed papers.

Dimension	Summary (Sector – Grouped Uncertainty Source – Associated Papers)
Climate	Power and Hydropower – Hydrological variability ([27], [32], [35]); Meteorological drivers ([41]); Hydro capacity factor [32]. Buildings – Weather and climatic conditions [30]. Cross-sectoral energy–climate – Climate model ensembles [37]; RCP pathways [18]. Food and land systems – Agricultural productivity impacts [21]. Renewable heating – Solar production and emission factors [36]. Land use and transport – Bundled climate uncertainty [45].

Socio-Economic	Energy – Population growth and demand sensitivities [17]; Willingness to pay for NEs [49]; Behavioural parameters [18]. Power/Electricity – GDP and energy intensity [38]; Electricity demand growth [19], [53], [54]; DR behavioural response [20]. Transport – EV charging demand [55]; EV shares [32]; Employment and elasticities [39]; Travel demand parameters [28]. Food and land systems – Diets and food [21]. Cross-sectoral economy – Economic activity and wages [33].
Political	Energy – Policy stability and timing [49]; National vision and strategy [17]. Climate–construction – Governance continuity [46]. Geothermal – Lender approval and governance delays [26]. Land use and transport – Bundled political uncertainty [45].
Policy / Regulatory	Electricity – Renewable targets and coal phase-out [38]; CO ₂ pricing [19], [34], [36]; Feed-in tariffs [35]. Energy – Market-based instruments [17], [49]; Climate policy timing [29]. Geothermal – Permits and institutional delays [26]. Transport – Vehicle regulations and taxation [28]. Food and land – Afforestation and expansion targets [21].
Techno-Economic	Power – Fuel prices [20], [34], [54]; Capital costs including storage [19], [29], [32], [38]; Transmission investment [53]. Energy – Grid losses and fossil shocks [17]; BECCS costs [49]; GGR costs [31]. Transport – Fuel and operating costs [28], [39]; NGV conversion costs [24]. Geothermal – Exploration and exploitation costs [26]; Cost overruns [35].
Technological	Power – Plant lifetimes [34]; ESS business models [19]; Capacity factor [52]; DR technical potential [20]. Energy – Learning effects and capacity potential [17]; BECCS efficiency [49]. Electricity – Battery capacity shares [38]. Transport – EV efficiency and EV share [39]; Advanced vehicle systems [28]. Geothermal – Drilling success and resource confirmation [26]. Food and land – Crop and livestock productivity growth [21].

Another finding related to the operationalisation of uncertainty concerns structural uncertainty. Structural uncertainty relates to alternative model formulations, boundary choices, and system representations and is acknowledged conceptually in some studies [23], [25], [37], [40], [47], mostly qualitatively. However, structural uncertainty remains largely unaddressed in the reviewed applications. Most studies operate within a fixed model structure and focus primarily on parametric variation. This gap is also highlighted in broader DMDU and robustness reviews [4], [59], [60], [61], [62], [63], suggesting a persistent divergence between the theoretical emphasis on deep structural uncertainty and its limited operationalisation in applied modelling practice.

3.3 Characterising decision outcomes

The DMDU workflow follows a structured sequence that moves from exploration to evaluation and adaptive redesign. It consists of framing the problem, exploring uncertainties, diagnosing vulnerabilities, evaluating robustness across plausible futures, and redesigning strategies through adaptive pathways supported by monitoring and contingent actions.

Formal vulnerability analysis remains comparatively concentrated. Scenario discovery techniques such as PRIM [24], [34], [36], [39], CART [49], Monte Carlo–based exploratory discovery [21], and regression trees [19] are used to identify combinations of uncertainties leading to failure. In several cases,

vulnerability is inferred implicitly through IGDT tolerance bands [52], [55] or sensitivity analysis [17], [25], [32], [33], [35] particularly in techno-economic applications. A notable group of studies remain upstream or conceptual, with no explicit vulnerability diagnostics [18], [23], [31], [40], [48], [51]. Even when studies operationalise robustness through threshold-based screening metrics, they stop short of explicit vulnerability mapping. In others, vulnerability remains implicit, inferred from dispersion in performance metrics across scenarios without formal diagnostics [28], [30], [32], [38]. Few studies adopt qualitative or governance-oriented approaches, identifying vulnerabilities through expert elicitation and narrative structuring rather than model-based metrics [23], [42], [43], [45], [46], [47].

Overall, robustness analysis is more frequently undertaken than explicit vulnerability diagnosis. A subset of papers employ formal robustness metrics, including minimax and minimax regret [30], [50], [53], IGDT robustness functions based on maximum admissible uncertainty horizons [52], [54], [55], satisficing robustness measured as the proportion of futures meeting predefined thresholds [21], [37], [39], financial robustness using NPV or payback criteria [35], [49], and novel screening metrics such as robust capacity and capacity-at-risk [29]. Other studies conduct robustness analysis through comparative performance assessment across large ensembles of futures without explicit scalar metrics [17], [32], [33], [38] or through qualitative pathway comparison [24], [44], [47].

Table 3. Vulnerability analysis and robustness metrics employed in the reviewed studies

Category	Technique / Description
Formal Robustness Metrics	Minimax, Minimax Regret, dispersion, Taguchi-type measures [30]
	Minimax regret [50], [53]
	IGDT robustness function (maximum uncertainty horizon α) [52], [54], [55]
	Satisficing robustness (% futures meeting thresholds) [21], [37], [39]
	Financial robustness (NPV / Payback threshold based) [35], [49]
	Robust capacity, Capacity at Risk, Risk Ratio [29]
	Trade-off robustness analysis (cost–emissions portfolios) [34]
	Multi-metric robustness comparison (Hurwicz, Laplace, mean–variance etc.) [41]
	Performance comparison across futures [28], [32], [33], [38]
	Ensemble stress-testing [17]
Robustness Analysis (No Formal Metric)	Profitability / viability across futures [19], [25]
	Comparative pathway assessment [47]
Vulnerability Identification	Conceptual robustness discussion [44], [64]
	PRIM scenario discovery [34], [36], [39], [64]

			CART [49]
			Monte Carlo scenario discovery [21]
			Supervised regression tree [19]
			Adaptation tipping points (capacity > demand thresholds) [42]
			Expert-derived qualitative vulnerabilities [43], [45], [46]
			Sensitivity analysis as vulnerability proxy [17], [26], [32], [35]
			Implicit vulnerability via IGDT tolerance bands [52], [55]
			Implicit vulnerability via ensemble divergence [27]
			Conceptual / upstream framing [18], [23], [31], [48], [51]
			Robust optimisation only (no vulnerability diagnosis) [50], [53]
			Robustness metric only, no diagnostic analysis [30], [41]
No	Explicit	Vulnerability	Narrative critique without modelling [40]
Assessment			

Even when drivers of vulnerability are identified and robustness is evaluated, these insights seldom translate into adaptive, decision-ready actions that are co-developed with stakeholders. Table 4 shows that full integration of stakeholder deliberation, exploratory modelling, and adaptive pathway design is rare across all decision levels. Except for one study [49], papers exhibit only one or two of these elements, revealing a fragmentation between stakeholder deliberation, exploratory modelling, and adaptive pathway design in the literature. [49] combines DAP and RDM, suggesting that hybrid methodological approaches create stronger integration between modelling, deliberation, and adaptive design. Similar integrative tendencies appear in [27], [48], reinforcing that methodological combinations foster richer stakeholder engagement and more actionable adaptive insights.

Table 4. Mapping stakeholder engagement, type of decision support and adaptive planning across reviewed studies

Decision Context	DMDU Approach Used	Stakeholder Pattern	Decision Support Type	Adaptive Planning Recommended	Paper IDs
Project	RDM inspired	No	Limited	No	[30]
	DAP + RDM	Yes	Yes	Yes	[49]
Investment	DAP	No	Yes	Partially	[50]
	IGDT	No	Yes	No	[53]
	RDM inspired / ROSS	No	Yes	No	[36], [41]

	EMA variants	Mixed	Conceptual to Yes	Limited/Partial	[23], [25], [26], [27], [65]
Policy	EMA	No	Enables	No	[18]
	DAPP	Yes	Conceptual	Yes	[43]
	RDM Conceptual	Yes	Yes	Conceptual	[40]
Strategy	RDM	Mixed	Limited to Yes	No	[31], [32], [33], [37], [38], [39]
	EMA	No	Limited to Yes	No	[17], [21], [28], [64], [66]
	DAPP	Yes	Conceptual to Yes	Conceptual	[44], [45], [46], [47]
System	EMA + DAPP	Yes	Yes	Conceptual	[48]
	IGDT	No	Yes	No	[52], [54], [55]
	RDM inspired / RDM	No	Yes	No	[34], [35]
	EMA inspired	No	Limited	No	[19], [20]
	DAP / DAPP	Mixed	Limited	Conceptual	[42], [51]

Few studies explicitly document stakeholder participation and institutional involvement. Several papers report broad multi-actor participation, including policymakers, planners, industry, and civil society [40], [46], [48], [51]. These studies often specify actor categories such as government bodies, private-sector organisations, grid operators, logistics stakeholders, modelling communities, and regulatory institutions. A subset of studies document formalised institutional collaboration, explicitly naming universities, ministries, and public agencies (e.g., Delft University of Technology and IIASA in [44]; Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Energy, PLN (electricity off-taker), and local government in [26]; Stockholm Exergi in [49]). Some studies highlight structured deliberative processes, such as including 30 bilateral meetings and large sectoral workshops [38] or board-level coordination and partner agency involvement [39]. Overall, studies that explicitly name institutions, actor categories, and engagement formats demonstrate greater procedural transparency and replicability.

Discussion

The review shows that stakeholder deliberation, exploratory modelling, and adaptive pathway design remain largely fragmented in the literature. This fragmentation underscores the continued relevance of “deliberation with analysis,” a concept introduced by Lempert, Popper, and Bankes (2003) in *Shaping the Next One Hundred Years*, which emphasises the iterative integration of stakeholder engagement and quantitative analysis in decision-making under deep uncertainty [1].

A strong “deliberation-with-analysis” workflow is to use stakeholders to (i) define success metrics, uncertainties, and candidate actions, (ii) translate those into a quantitative uncertainty experiment (EMA/RDM), and then (iii) convert the resulting vulnerabilities and robust options into an adaptive pathway with signposts/triggers and contingent actions. Figure 3 illustrates the proposed workflow (inspired by Figure 1 in [42], [49]).

The workflow consists of the following three phases.

Phase 1: Stakeholder-led problem structuring

The process begins with structured stakeholder engagement to define objectives, constraints, performance thresholds, policy levers, and key uncertainties, similar to Stage 1 described in [43]. Rather than treating participation as a one-off consultation exercise, this phase formalises stakeholder inputs into model-ready structures, such as XLRM framing of RDM [67], ensuring that uncertainties reflect decision-relevant concerns and that performance metrics represent socially and politically meaningful definitions of success. By grounding the modelling exercise in co-defined objectives and uncertainty spaces, Phase 1 establishes the analytical contract between stakeholders and modellers. In [44], Q-statements and stakeholder dialogues translate qualitative stakeholder perspectives into quantitative model constraints and produce structured inputs that modellers can directly use for exploratory modelling, scenario discovery, and robustness analysis.

Phase 2: Translating stakeholder perspectives into quantitative uncertainty space and evaluating robustness

In contrast to conventional linear modelling exercises, exploratory modelling and robustness evaluation are treated here as a combined analytical–deliberative phase. Large ensembles of plausible futures are generated by varying identified uncertainties, candidate strategies are evaluated across these futures, and scenario discovery techniques are used to identify the drivers of vulnerability and conditions under which strategies fail to meet stakeholder-defined thresholds [4].

Next, for robustness evaluation, the analytical results are brought back to stakeholders for interpretation (Step 3 described in [43]). This iterative loop enables participants to deliberate on trade-offs, reconsider acceptable risks, refine strategy portfolios, and explore adaptive options. By merging exploratory modelling, scenario discovery, and stakeholder deliberation, Phase 2 operationalises “deliberation with analysis” [8] as an interactive learning process rather than a post-hoc validation step.

Phase 3: Integrating insights into dynamic adaptive pathway design

The final phase translates analytical insights into dynamic adaptive policy pathways. Vulnerabilities identified in Phase 2 are reframed as adaptation tipping points or conditions requiring monitoring (see Tables 3 and 4 in [49] and Table 4 in [43]). Strategies are sequenced over time, with explicit signposts, trigger conditions, and contingent actions defined in advance (see Stages 4 and 5 in [43]). This phase shifts the focus from identifying a single robust strategy to designing adaptive pathways that remain flexible under evolving uncertainties (as in Figure 6 in [42]).

Furthermore, this phase embeds a structured monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system that tracks signposts and trigger thresholds over time. When predefined trigger levels are reached and adaptive actions are implemented, the decision cycle is reactivated: strategies are re-evaluated, uncertainties are reassessed, and the exploratory analysis is updated as necessary. The iterative learning loop ensures that the framework functions not as a one-time robustness assessment but as a continuous adaptive decision-support system. By explicitly linking quantitative vulnerability analysis to adaptive pathway design, the framework closes the loop between uncertainty analysis and real-world decision processes.

Figure 3. Proposed hybrid deliberation-with-analysis workflow.

Thus, a deliberation-with-analysis workflow that iteratively consolidates exploratory modelling and robustness deliberation offers a co-decision-oriented extension to predominant analysis-centric DMDU applications. It advances the literature by moving beyond exploratory assessment toward adaptive decision support in a structured and operational manner co-developed with stakeholders.

Conclusion

The reviewed literature shows a gradual transition from single-method applications toward more exploratory and hybrid frameworks in the post-2020 period. DMDU applications remain heavily concentrated in high-income country contexts, pointing to a clear need for greater uptake in LMIC settings where uncertainty and infrastructure lock-in risks are often more acute. Moreover, political and structural uncertainties are rarely quantified. Stakeholder deliberation, exploratory modelling, and adaptive pathway design remain largely fragmented in the existing literature, revealing a critical gap in the structured integration of participatory processes with formal robustness and vulnerability analysis for developing adaptive designs and decisions. Addressing these gaps is essential for advancing DMDU from methodological experimentation toward fully integrated, decision-centred practice in long-term energy planning.

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Appendices

Appendix A

TITLE-ABS-KEY(("Paris agreement" OR decarbonisation OR ((energy OR transport* OR electricity OR grid OR "power system" OR electrification OR "low carbon") AND (planning OR polic* OR expansion OR pathway OR plan OR roadmap OR transition* OR invest*)) OR "net zero" OR "climate change mitigation") AND uncertainty) AND("info gap decision theory" OR "engineering options analysis" OR "exploratory systems dynamics model*ing and analysis" OR "interactive epoch era analysis" OR "adaptive policy pathway" OR "exploratory mode*ing" OR "scenario discovery" OR "exploratory scenario analysis" OR "robust optimisation" OR "minimax regret" OR "least worst regret" OR "decision making under deep uncertainty" OR ((robust* OR adaptive OR flexible) W/3 (polic* OR strateg* OR "decision making" OR plan OR planning)) OR "mode*ing to generate alternatives") AND ("non probabilistic uncertainty" OR "genuine uncertainty" OR "great uncertainty" OR "epistemic uncertainty" OR "fundamental uncertainty" OR "irreducible uncertainty" OR "severe uncertainty" OR "radical uncertainty" OR "deep* uncertain*" OR "Knightian uncertainty") AND NOT KEY (water OR "day ahead" OR "real time" OR "optimal dispatch")